

Intelligent Duty Cycling Management and Wake-up for Energy Harvesting IoT Networks with Correlated Activity

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Abstract—This paper presents an approach for energy-neutral Internet of Things (IoT) scenarios where the IoT devices (IoTDs) operate solely on harvested energy. We use a Markov chain to represent the operation and transmission states of the IoTDs, a modulated Poisson process to model their energy harvesting process, and a discrete-time Markov chain to model their battery state. The aim is to efficiently manage the duty cycling of the IoTDs, so as to prolong their battery life and reduce instances of low-energy availability. We propose a duty-cycling management based on K- nearest neighbors, aiming to strike a trade-off between energy efficiency and detection accuracy. This is done by incorporating spatial and temporal correlations among IoTDs' activity, as well as their energy harvesting capabilities. We also allow the base station to wake up specific IoTDs if more information about an event is needed upon initial detection. Our proposed scheme shows significant improvements in energy savings and performance, with up to 11 times lower misdetection probability and 50% lower energy consumption for high-density scenarios compared to a random duty cycling benchmark.

Index Terms—Duty cycling, energy harvesting, Internet of Things, K-nearest neighbors, wake-up.

I. INTRODUCTION

Achieving sustainable development in today's society requires technological solutions balancing economic growth, social equity, and environmental integrity. In this context, the Internet of Things (IoT) plays a crucial role by connecting devices for mobility, safety, environmental, and resource monitoring [1], [2]. In the sixth generation (6G) networks, achieving

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sustainability becomes even more critical due to the huge IoT device (IoTD) expected density, highlighting the urgent need to minimize IoTDs' energy consumption and enhance resource utilization to deliver high performance [3].

To tackle sustainability issues in IoT ecosystems, it is crucial to rely less on external power sources and instead use energy harvesting (EH) techniques. This, together with resource allocation optimization for energy efficiency [4], promotes energy autonomy. Several techniques such as wake-up receivers (WuRs) and discontinuous reception (DRX) are being explored to increase the battery life of devices and reduce energy waste. Specifically, WuRs have the potential to save up to 1,000 times [5] the energy consumed by the main radio interface, allowing IoTDs to transition to a sleep state while the WuR remains active [6], [7]. However, these methods may not always yield the desired results, owing to the irregular traffic patterns of IoTDs [5]. Also, IoTDs relying solely on ambient EH sources for charging suffer from uncertain energy availability, jeopardizing their ability to recharge a limited battery and remain operational. This makes it difficult to coordinate the amount of energy available in each device and manage the duty cycling accordingly to extend the network's lifetime, scalability, and availability for proper functioning, and to ensure that the network is self-sustainable during its lifetime. Monitoring the network and keeping track of the IoTDs' traffic generation, and incoming energy availability simultaneously is an extremely challenging task [1]. In this sense, machine learning (ML) techniques have proven to characterize well the spatio-temporal nature of IoT traffic generation. ML can optimize resource allocation, predict system changes, and enhance energy efficiency in

Fig. 1. Illustration of an IoT network where the BS controls and collects information from various IoTDs. The impact of an event on the surrounding IoTDs is modeled through a probability activation function that decays with the distance (meters) from the event epicenter to the IoTDs.

IoT networks [8]. However, despite the benefits, ML-based methods for adjusting WuR and duty cycling parameters in self-sustaining IoT networks have not been explored, offering potential for further energy efficiency.

In several IoT scenarios, IoTDs are deployed to sense/detect events/alarms, as depicted in Fig. 1. Aiming for self-sustainable IoT deployments, these IoTDs may rely on energy harvested from the environment and an efficient energy consumption to remain operational. To ensure this, it is crucial to implement energy efficient mechanisms that allow the IoTDs to alternate between idle/sensing and sleep states. This duty cycling mode guarantees high energy availability for operation. Achieving a sustainable IoT deployment requires the integration of low-power WuR architecture, energy efficient duty cycling configuration, and efficient EH. Therefore, a comprehensive approach that integrates these technologies with intelligent solutions is essential for a sustainable IoT deployment. In this paper, we aim to efficiently manage the duty cycling in an energy-neutral IoT scenario, extend the battery life of IoTDs, and use WuR to avoid misdetected events while avoiding low-energy availability. Specifically, the contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- We address an energy-neutral IoT scenario where the IoTDs harvest ambient energy and monitor the occurrence of events/alarms while in the sensing state. Upon the detection of an event/alarm, they transmit this information to the BS. We employ a four-state Markov chain to represent the operation and transmission states of the IoTDs. The energy harvesting availability is modeled as modulated Poisson processes (MPP), and the battery state as a discrete Markov chain.
- We propose a K-nearest neighbors (KNN)-based duty cycling configuration that considers both energy efficiency and the likelihood of event misdetection. This perspective considers spatial and temporal correlations among IoTDs.
- We propose a wake-up method for WuR-equipped IoTDs. The BS can wake up certain IoTDs if more information about the event is needed. Herein, the wake-up process is

managed based on the spatial correlation among IoTDs.

- We show the improvement in energy saving and performance from our proposal with up to 11 times less misdetection probability and 50% decrease in energy consumption for high-density scenarios compared to a random duty cycling baseline.

To the best of our knowledge, optimizing duty cycling in this type of scenario has not been proposed before. Our research is particularly important as the number of IoTDs rises, making essential to reduce their energy consumption to meet operational requirements and achieve sustainable IoT networks.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we present the system model along with the analysis of EH and event influence. Section IV outlines the optimization problem for the duty cycling setup, while Section V-A proposes solutions based on heuristics and ML. The effectiveness of the proposed methods is evaluated through numerical simulations in Section VI. Finally, we conclude the paper in Section VII.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider the coverage area of a BS serving as gateway for a set \mathcal{N} of N IoTDs with EH capabilities as depicted in Fig. 1. These IoTDs are deployed to identify event triggers, such as a moving object in motion detection applications or a fire in a fire-alarm system. Moreover, the time is slotted in transmission time intervals (TTIs) with duration τ . We assume that the position of each IoTD is known by the coordinator and that events occur uniformly in the area with probability α in each TTI [5]. The IoTDs can operate in four different states $S_m \in \mathcal{S}$, with $m \in [1, 2, 3, 4]$:

- 1) idle state (S_1), wherein the IoTDs wait to be triggered by an event;
- 2) active state (S_2), wherein the IoTD is triggered by an event and aims to send the information to the BS;
- 3) transmission state (S_3), wherein the IoTD sends the information to the BS;
- 4) sleep state (S_4), wherein the IoTD stays at low-power state and harvests energy.

We denote $P_{m,n}^{(j)}$ as the transition probability for IoTD j from a state S_m into a state S_n . The states and their transition probabilities are illustrated with a discrete-time Markov process, as shown in Fig. 2.

A device goes from S_1 to S_2 with probability $P_{1,2}^{(j)}$ upon detecting an alarm event, indicating the need for data transmission to the BS. IoTDs in S_2 with high-energy availability transmit the information corresponding to the detected events according to their battery level with probability $P_{2,3}^{(j)}$, while those with low-energy availability cannot transmit the information and go to S_4 awaiting to harvest enough energy for future events. Notice that an IoTD with high-energy availability can alternate between S_1 and S_4 with probabilities $P_{4,1}^{(j)}$ and $P_{1,4}^{(j)}$ based on their duty cycling configuration and energy availability.

Fig. 2. Device's operation states modeled as a four states discrete-time Markov chain.

We define $p(d_j^{(i)})$ as a sensing power function for IoT D_j while in S_1 , representing the impact of the i^{th} event with epicenter at (x_i, y_i) , within the network area $\xi \subset \mathbb{R}^2$. Here, $d_j^{(i)}$ indicates the distance between them. Note that, $p(d_j^{(i)}) : [0, \infty) \rightarrow (0, 1]$ is non-increasing to model a decaying influence of events as the distance $d_j^{(i)}$ increases. Fig.1 illustrates an example of the influence of an event epicenter on the surrounding IoT D_j . In this paper, we assume an exponentially decreasing function, i.e., $p(d_j^{(i)}) = e^{-\eta d_j^{(i)}}$ [5]. Here, the parameter η ($\eta > 0$) controls the average sensitivity for a given distance. Furthermore, we assume that the temporal correlation with the event is instantaneous while the spatial correlation depends on $p(d_j^{(i)})$. Active devices transmit packets to the BS, managing all information exchanges within its cell [5]. Assume equal transmission power for all IoT D_j . In a TTI k and state S_2 (active), devices generate traffic, while no traffic is generated in the other states.

Active IoT D_j s send information about the detected event. The level of information sent by each device corresponds to the detected entropy of the event itself. In this study, we model this relationship of detected information using the sensing power function of each IoT D_j in S_2 as follows:

$$I_j^{(i)} = \Psi p(d_j^{(i)}), \quad (1)$$

where $\Psi > 0$ constitutes the maximum amount of information that an IoT D_j can detect. The BS gathers the information reported by the IoT D_j s while keeping the one that best describes the event (i). Therefore, the information about event i at the BS is given by

$$I^{(i)} = \max(I_j^{(i)}), \forall j \text{ in } S_2. \quad (2)$$

If no IoT D_j detects the event, then $I^{(i)} = 0$.

Our model uses discrete energy harvesting and storage for device batteries, which have maximum capacity E_{\max} when fully charged. Additionally, transmitting in S_2 results in a depletion of E_{Tx} units, while monitoring events in S_1 consumes E_{idle} units per TTI, as depicted in Fig. 3. We assume that, if the battery level (B) of an IoT D_j at the moment of transmissions is lower than the level needed to transmit or perform event monitoring, the battery is depleted and the

Fig. 3. Illustration of the battery level evolution by considering the energy consumption and EH models. Transmission (TX) results in the highest energy depletion, while sleep is a low-energy consumption state. Sensing results in a depletion smaller than TX but greater than in a sleep state.

action is unsuccessful. We also assume that the BS knows or at least predicts the battery level of the devices according to the information received from those IoT D_j s in S_3 . This approach helps to conserve power by not prompting a device with low energy levels to wake up and transmit information. Such an action would otherwise drain the battery, and even if the device were to transmit, the information would not be received due to the lack of energy required for transmission.

In this paper, we adopt a simplified model based on [5] that refers only to the energy consumption of the radio frequency interface. Specifically, the mean energy consumption (\overline{EC}) is calculated based on the energy consumption of battery units (EC_m) for every state S_m . This is summarized as the energy units consumed per IoT D_j per TTI and written as

$$\overline{EC} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^4 \Pr(S_m^{(j)}) EC_m. \quad (3)$$

At each TTI, we also model the energy harvested by the IoT D_j s by using N MPPs, one for each IoT D_j . Specifically, a Poisson process is used to describe the occurrence of energy arrival within a certain time interval. The time duration for the occurrence of energy arrival, i.e., the time duration in case the energy source remains active, is modeled with an exponential distribution with mean μ_j . At each TTI (k), the energy arrival from an energy source occurs at maximum only once. In that case, the energy source can be considered as active or inactive within one time slot, as shown in Fig. 3. By defining the parameters $\lambda_j = 1/\mu_j$, the probability of the energy source being active within one TTI can be expressed as

$$p_j = \lambda_j \tau \exp(-\lambda_j \tau), k = 1, 2, \dots, K. \quad (4)$$

III. BATTERY STATE EVOLUTION

The probability that an IoT D_j has sufficient energy in the battery to perform transmission or sensing depends on the energy harvested at each TTI plus the initial battery level and previous actions performed by the IoT D_j . To calculate this probability, we can use a discrete-time Markov chain to model the battery level over time. We define states for the battery

level, while transitions occur based on the energy harvesting process and the battery consumption operations.

Following the MPP, it is possible to harvest energy with a probability $\exp(-\lambda_j)$. We formulate a discrete Markov chain with states representing the battery level (from 0 to E_{\max} units). Let's denote the states of the battery level as follows:

- State 0: Battery level is 0 units;
- State 1: Battery level is λ_j units;
- State 2: Battery level is $2\lambda_j$ units;
- ...
- State $\lceil E_{\max}/\lambda_j \rceil$: Battery level is E_{\max} units.

We calculate the transition probabilities between these states based on the energy harvesting process and battery consumption operations. Assuming a steady state, the state arrival rate is equal to the state departure rate. Therefore, we can use the fact that $\sum_{B=0}^{\lceil E_{\max}/\lambda_j \rceil} r_B = 1$, where r_B is the steady B state probability, to solve the next equation system $P_B \times R_B = C$, where $C = [1, 1, \dots, 1]^T$,

$$P_B = \begin{pmatrix} B_{0,0} & B_{0,1} & \cdots & B_{0,\lceil E_{\max}/\lambda_j \rceil} \\ B_{1,0} & B_{1,1} & \cdots & B_{1,\lceil E_{\max}/\lambda_j \rceil} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ B_{\lceil E_{\max}/\lambda_j \rceil,0} & B_{\lceil E_{\max}/\lambda_j \rceil,1} & \cdots & B_{\lceil E_{\max}/\lambda_j \rceil,\lceil E_{\max}/\lambda_j \rceil} \\ 1 & 1 & \cdots & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

is the transition matrix, and $R_B = [r_0, r_1, \dots, r_{\lceil E_{\max}/\lambda_j \rceil}]^T$.

Next, we aim to find the probability of being in a state with sufficient battery to perform the operation that needs E_{Tx} units, *i.e.*, $\Pr(B \geq E_{\text{Tx}})$. Note that a device goes to state S_2 with probability $P_{1,2}^{(j)} + P_{4,2}^{(j)}$. While in S_2 , we need to check whether the IoTD has sufficient energy to transmit the sensed information. Exploiting the previously presented Markov chain with states representing B , we obtain $\Pr(B^{(j)} \geq E_{\text{Tx}})$ as

$$\sum_{x=B_{E_{\text{Tx}}}}^{B_{\lceil E_{\max}/\lambda_j \rceil}} \binom{x}{E_{\text{Tx}}} (P_{1,2}^{(j)} - P_{4,2}^{(j)})^{E_{\text{Tx}}} (1 - P_{1,2}^{(j)} - P_{4,2}^{(j)})^{x-E_{\text{Tx}}}, \quad (6)$$

which has a semi-closed form using the regularized incomplete beta function, $\beta_{1-P_{2,1}^{(j)}-P_{3,1}^{(j)}}(E_{\text{Tx}}+1, E_{\max}+1)$, with parameters $E_{\text{Tx}}+1$ and $E_{\max}+1$ [9]. We can similarly calculate $\Pr(B^{(j)} \geq E_{\text{idle}})$, *i.e.*, the probability that the IoTD is able to sense in S_1 .

IV. ON-DEMAND WAKE-UP AND TRANSITION PROBABILITIES

In this paper, we propose equipping IoTDs with WuR modules to detect requests from the BS to either enter the active state (S_2) or switch between states. The WuR module allows IoTDs with low-energy availability to remain in state S_4 while also ensuring their availability to provide additional information to the BS when required ($P_{4,2}^{(j)}$). The BS may try to wake up certain IoTDs in S_4 to sense potential events based on information received from other IoTDs and their spatial correlation. However, this might not always be possible

because IoTDs with a low-energy availability stay in S_4 (with probability $P_{4,4}^{(j)}$) and harvest energy for future events (if enough energy becomes available). Meanwhile, IoTDs in S_4 with high-energy availability may be authorized by the BS to move from S_4 to S_1 for the purpose of monitoring potential events.

Transitions between states can occur as follows.

- 1) A transition from S_4 to S_1 occurs during the ON time of the duty cycling, then $P_{4,1}^{(j)} = \frac{\text{ON time}}{\text{DRX cycle}}$, where DRX cycle accounts for the time between consecutive ON states (S_1). Otherwise, the IoTD stays on S_4 with probability $P_{4,4}^{(j)} = 1 - P_{4,1}^{(j)} - P_{4,2}^{(j)}$.
- 2) A transition from S_4 to S_2 occurs when the BS needs more information about an event. To determine this transition, we use the conditional probability $\Pr(S_3^{(j)}|S_3^{(h)})$, which represents the probability that an IoTD j is in state S_3 , given that another IoTD h is in state S_3 . We then assign the maximum conditional probability as $P_{4,2}^{(j)} = \max_h (\Pr(S_3^{(j)}|S_3^{(h)}))$ with respect to the active IoTDs h in state S_3 , $\forall h$ in S_3 . Herein, $\Pr(S_3^{(j)}|S_3^{(h)})$ is determined by the spatial correlation between the j^{th} IoTD and each h in S_3 . We calculate $\Pr(S_3^{(j)}|S_3^{(h)})$ using the cosine rule as follows

$$d_j^{(i)2} = d_h^{(i)2} + d_{j,h}^2 - 2d_h^{(i)}d_{j,h} \cos \varphi, \quad (7)$$

where $d_{j,h}$ the distance between both devices and φ is the angle between $d_h^{(i)}$ and $d_{j,h}$, as depicted in Fig. 1. Then, $\Pr(S_3^{(j)}|S_3^{(h)})$ is given by

$$\exp\left(-\eta\sqrt{d_h^{(i)2} + d_{j,h}^2 - 2d_h^{(i)}d_{j,h} \cos \varphi}\right), \quad (8)$$

where d_h , $d_{j,h}$, and φ are known.

- 3) A transition from S_1 to S_2 for an event (i) occurs with probability $P_{1,2}^{(j)} = \alpha p(d_j^{(i)})$. Otherwise, the IoTD stays in S_1 with probability $P_{1,1}^{(j)} = \sum_{i=1}^{\text{ON time}} (1 - \alpha)^i \frac{\text{ON time} - i}{\text{DRX cycle} - i}$, while transits from S_1 to S_4 with probability $P_{1,4}^{(j)} = 1 - P_{1,1}^{(j)} - P_{1,2}^{(j)}$.
- 4) A transition from S_2 to S_3 occurs when B is enough to transmit, thus $P_{2,3}^{(j)} = \Pr(B \geq E_{\text{Tx}})$, while the device transits from S_2 to S_4 , with probability $P_{2,4}^{(j)} = 1 - P_{2,3}^{(j)}$.
- 5) A transition from S_3 to S_1 occurs with probability $P_{3,1}^{(j)} = \sum_{i=1}^{\text{On time}} \frac{\text{On time} - i}{\text{DRX cycle} - i}$, while the transition from S_3 to S_4 occurs with probability $P_{3,4}^{(j)} = 1 - P_{3,1}^{(j)}$.

V. OPTIMIZATION FRAMEWORK

An IoTD duty cycling and wake-up management policy is referred to as $\delta(k) = [\delta_1(k), \delta_2(k), \dots, \delta_N(k)]^T$ for each TTI $k \in [0, K]$. At each TTI k , $\delta(k)$ designates which IoTD will be in S_1 , waiting to be triggered or waken-up from S_4 to S_2 (designated by 1), and which device will remain in S_4 (designated by 0). Here, $\delta(k)$ must take into account $\Pr(B^{(j)} \geq E_{\text{idle}})$ and $\Pr(B^{(j)} \geq E_{\text{Tx}})$ due to the energy arrivals at random times and the finite battery storage capacity.

By considering a long time interval (*i.e.*, large K), minimizing the probability of missing events mainly depends on the availability of energy in the battery of the IoTDs. Reducing energy consumption means having a greater density of IoTDs with high energy availability for event sensing and reporting. This in turn leads to fewer blind spots where events may go unnoticed, consequently decreasing the misdetection probability. Then, we formulate the optimization problem as

$$\text{P1: } \min_{\delta(k)} \overline{\text{EC}} \quad (9a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \frac{1}{\alpha K} \sum_{\forall(i)} I^{(i)} \geq I_{\min}, \quad (9b)$$

where I_{\min} is the minimum expected information per event. Here, we use the expected number of events, αK , as normalization factor instead of the exact number of events since the latter cannot be known. Herein, $\overline{\text{EC}}$ can be reformulated from (3) as

$$\overline{\text{EC}} = \frac{1}{NK} \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{j=1}^N \delta_j(k) (E_{\text{idle}} + \Pr(S_3^{(j)}) E_{\text{Tx}}). \quad (10)$$

Note that at each TTI k , IoTDs with $\delta_j = 0$ consume no energy in sleep mode S_4 while IoTDs with $\delta_j = 1$ need high energy availability for sensing/transmit. Therefore, proper $\delta(k)$ management is crucial at each TTI.

Satisfying a minimum expected information per event necessitates maintaining IoTDs' sensing/reporting availability. That is maintaining the battery level of IoTDs above the threshold required for transmission. Only these devices have the capability to transmit event information. At the same time, proper sensing cycling and wake-up strategy helps to reduce energy consumption and avoid misdetections, which worsen the mean information per event.

Optimization methods to solve this problem can be both computationally intensive and time-consuming, particularly in the context of large-scale IoT systems where the complexity of performing interior point method can increase significantly, scaling with the number of IoTDs as $\mathcal{O}(N^\rho)$, with $\rho \in [3, 4]$ [10]. In light of this, we aim to propose heuristic and data-driven approaches to address the issue in a more computationally efficient manner. Heuristic approaches, while potentially providing near-optimal solutions within a short time-frame, rely on intuitive rules or strategies.

A. Heuristic & KNN-based Duty Cycling Optimization

Herein, we outline the potential approaches to tackle the problem at hand. The proposed approach is summarized in Algorithm 1. Specifically, we propose two approaches. In the first one, we optimize the IoTD duty cycling by using an exhaustive search within the ON time (S_1) and DRX cycle¹ values. In the second one, we form clusters in line 2 of Algorithm 1 based on each device's spatial placement. We create a graph structure using KNN method as follows: (1)

¹The duration of ON time (S_1) plus sleep time (S_4) within a cycle constitutes the DRX cycle.

Algorithm 1 KNN-based solution

- 1: **Set** number of clusters (M) as $M = \xi/(\pi d_{\max}^2)$
 - 2: **Form** clusters using KNN method
 - 3: **Configure** duty cycling of IoTDs according to its cluster association (ON time = 1, duty cycle = cluster size)
 - 4: **for** each k **do**
 - 5: **if** BS receives information from active IoTDs **then**
 - 6: $\hat{I}^{(i)} = \max(I_h^{(i)}), \forall h$ in S_3
 - 7: **if** $\hat{I}^{(i)} < I_{\min}$ **then**
 - 8: BS sequentially activates IoTDs $\forall j$ in S_4
with $\Pr(S_3^{(j)} | S_3^{(h)}) \geq p(d_{\max}), \forall h$ in S_3 , starting with the one with the highest value while updating $\hat{I}^{(i)} = \max(\hat{I}^{(i)}, I_j^{(i)}), \forall j$ in S_3
 - 9: **end if**
 - 10: **Update** $I^{(i)} \leftarrow \hat{I}^{(i)}$
 - 11: **end if**
 - 12: **end for**
-

set cluster number randomly, (2) calculate the distance to the neighbors, (3) identify each IoTD KNN based on the distances, and (4) assign each IoTD to the cluster that the majority of its KNN belong to, and (5) update centroids and repeat (2-5) until convergence [11]. The algorithm sets a maximum distance d_{\max} in line 1, which corresponds to the minimum sensing power $p(d_{\max})$ set to form the clusters. The aim is to reduce the misdetection probability by limiting the sensing area that the clusters must control. Then, at line 3, we configure the duty cycling of the IoTDs in each cluster. In each TTI, the IoTDs within a cluster iterate the sensing in S_1 . That is, during each TTI, only one IoTD is actively sensing in S_1 while the other IoTDs in the cluster are in S_4 , ensuring there is always one IoTD in S_1 during each TTI. In each cluster, the DRX cycle duration for IoTDs within that cluster is equal to the number of IoTDs in that cluster.

In both approaches, the BS may request more information about an event from the other devices in S_4 that have strong spatial correlation with the IoTDs in S_3 , as in line 7. In this way, the BS just requests the information that is needed using the WuR technology. Herein, we maintain the level of information that the BS requires from an event above a threshold (I_{\min}), having access to more information or a certain level of information from IoTDs enhances the BS's ability to effectively manage the network, respond to events, and ensure the overall reliability and performance of the IoT system. Note that a shorter DRX cycle decreases the misdetection probability when there is high energy availability, however, it increases the energy consumption and the risk of low energy availability. Then, a trade-off between energy saving and sensing availability to lower the misdetection probability is paramount.

Notice that the first approach differentiates from the second one in the way the duty cycling is configured. Indeed, the BS wake-up request for the first approach is according to the device's correlation rather than cluster-based as in Algorithm 1.

B. Complexity Analysis

The first approach of optimizing the duty cycling involves an exhaustive search within the ON time and DRX cycle. However, this method has a significant computational cost, with a complexity of $\mathcal{O}(g^N)$. Here, g is equal to the number of possible ON time values multiplied by the number of possible DRX cycle values. On the other hand, the second approach implementing KNN is bounded to $\mathcal{O}(N(N-1)/2)$. Such a worst-case complexity arises due to the distance computation to the N IoTD for each query point using a brute-force approach. The search involves scanning through the entire dataset to identify the KNN, resulting in a linear time complexity. However, as previously mentioned, the computation time can differ based on the utilized algorithm, occasionally reducing to $\mathcal{O}(\min\{M(N-M), (N-M)^2\})$, where M is the number of clusters [11].

VI. SIMULATIONS

We consider a 20×20 m² area with $N \in [10, 250]$ devices since $N < 10$ is not enough to cover the area, provoking many misdetection events. We perform 10^3 runs of Monte Carlo simulations with different deployments in each run and 10^4 TTIs, while assuming $\eta = 1$ [5] and $I_{\min} = \exp(-2)$. In addition, we assume $E_{\text{Tx}} = 10$ units while $E_{\text{idle}} = 1$ unit, and $p(d_{\max}) = 0.018$ corresponding to $d_{\max} = 4$ meters [8]. We assume IoTDs experiencing energy harvesting processes with the same statistics, *i.e.*, $\lambda_j = \lambda, \forall j \in \mathcal{N}$.

A. Benchmarks

We consider two benchmarks. In the first one, we let each device to adopt a random duty cycling with ON time $\in [1, 2]$ and DRX cycle $\in [2, 4, 8]$. For the second one, we adopt a genie-aided approach wherein the closest IoTD to the event epicenter always detects the event. It is important to mention that this approach is not feasible in practice. This is because the BS would need to know in advance which IoTD is the closest to the event epicenter in order to activate it using WuR. However, this approach provides a reference lower bound.

B. Performance Comparison

In Fig. 4, we present the misdetection probability for each configuration as a function of the device density. It is worth noting that the misdetection probability decreases as the device density increases. For instance, when there are only 10 IoTDs, the misdetection probability is around 33% for the cluster-based proposal, while for the duty cycling proposal is 58%, and 77% for the random duty cycling benchmark. The reason for this is that there might be blind spots in the deployment, that is no IoTDs near certain event occurrences. However, as the IoTD density increases, the probability drops below 3% for the proposed KNN-based solution. For the random duty cycling benchmark, the misdetection probability drops to a minimum of 7% for 250 IoTDs. Notice that the KNN-based solution outperforms both the optimal duty cycling proposal and the random duty cycling benchmark. Even though the optimal duty cycling can outperform the benchmark by up to

Fig. 4. Percentage of misdetected events.

a 200%, just optimizing the duty cycling is not enough to lower the misdetection probability below 4% in high density scenarios. Note that with the genie-aided approach, the misdetection probability drops from 2% to near 0.005% as we increase the IoTD density. This is because IoTDs have higher energy availability, as they do not need to waste energy on sensing while there is no event happening. However, there is still a small probability that the IoTD that detected the event does not have enough energy to transmit, as shown by this 0.005%.

Hereinafter, we also investigate the mean energy consumption per device per TTI as the density of IoTDs increases. The results depicted in Fig. 5 show that the mean energy consumption for the proposal methods is around 0.55-0.57 units per IoTD per TTI, while for the random duty cycling benchmark, it is around 0.34 units for 10 IoTDs. However, this consumption is according to the random duty cycling benchmark poor performance in detecting the events. As the device density increases, the mean energy consumption decreases up to 0.088 units for the proposed KNN-based method. In contrast, the mean energy consumption for the random duty cycling benchmark is above 0.18 units per TTI, which means that energy consumption increases by more than 100%. Notably, for more than 40 IoTDs, the mean energy consumption of the proposed KNN-based method is lower than for the random duty cycling benchmark. Additionally, our proposed method shows better performance, as seen in Fig. 4, where the misdetection probability is 11 times lower. It is worth-noting that the lower misdetection probability in the duty cycling proposal translates into a higher energy consumption for low-density scenarios. However, this gap disappears as the IoTD density increases. Meanwhile, compared to the genie-aided approach, the energy consumption to avoid misdetection of events is up to three times more for low density scenarios when using the KNN-based proposal. However, as the IoTD density increases, using the KNN approach can help reduce the gap in energy consumption. In high density scenarios, this approach can result in a reduction of up to 0.088 units per IoTD per TTI, compared to 0.055 units per IoTD with the

Fig. 5. Mean Energy consumption per device per TTI.

Fig. 6. Mean information received by the BS per event.

genie-aided approach. This translates to just a 39% increase in energy consumption compared with the genie-aided.

In Fig. 6, we show the average information received by the BS per event. It is worth noting that we have established $I_{\min} = \exp(-2)$ and that the proposed KNN-based method converges around this value for more than 25 IoTDS, whereas the random duty cycling benchmark is not able to reach this I_{\min} for values below 200 IoTDS. On the other hand, the information provided by the duty cycling proposal increases with the density of IoTDS. This is because more IoTDS are active at the same time, providing more information than the BS requests and increasing the mean energy consumption. Note that with the genie-aided method, the BS always obtains more than the minimum requested information from the event.

It is essential to note that using the proposed KNN-based method requires a higher computational cost. However, the proposed method runs on the BS, and the cost for the IoTDS is negligible. Moreover, the KNN-based proposal can be performed offline with the spatial information of the IoTDS.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

IoT sustainable development requires comprehensive strategies integrating energy-efficient technologies and optimized

resource allocation methods. This paper focused on efficiently managing IoT resources by extending device battery life and addressing low-energy availability. We modeled an IoT network with energy harvesting capabilities, employing a four-state Markov chain to depict IoTDS' states and modulated Poisson processes for energy harvesting availability. Additionally, the battery state was modeled as a discrete-time Markov chain. We proposed duty cycling configurations for IoTDS and using a wake-up method with WuR to minimize mean energy consumption, while considering spatial-temporal correlations and energy efficiency trade-offs. The results demonstrated significant improvements in energy savings and performance compared with a random duty cycling benchmark, with up to 11 times less misdetection probability and a more than 50% reduction in energy consumption observed in high-density scenarios.

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